

Gram scale continuous flow synthesis of silver-on-silica patchy particles with widely tunable plasmon resonances

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Supporting information

Movie S1: HAADF-STEM tilt series of several silver patches on two silica particles. Covering a tilt range of 140° with a projection every 1°.

Movie S2: 3D volume reconstruction of HAADF-STEM tilt series shown in Movie S1.

Movie S3: 3D slicing through one reconstructed silver patch highlighting its central protrusion and its dimension.

Table S1. Seeding and patch synthesis parameters used for the samples shown in this work

		Seeding			Patch synthesis				
	Seed batch (where relevant)	AuNc size acc. to Haiss et al. during seeding / nm	$\rho_{0,Seed}$ / -	c(AgNO ₃) / μ M	c(s-SiO ₂) / mg/L	c(CH ₂ O) / mM	c(NH ₃) / mM	n* $\times 10^{-6}$ / -	
Fig. 1 b-d)		4.5	20	-	-	-	-		
Fig. 3		4.2	40	60.00	90.00	80.58	34.00	1.222	
			20					2.444	
			10					4.889	
			5					9.778	
Fig. 4		4.2	20	60.00	90.00	80.58	34.00	2.444	
Fig. 5 / Fig. S6	A	4.3	40	30.00	90.00	80.58	34.00	0.611	
				45.00				0.917	
				60.00				1.222	
				75.00				1.528	
				90.00				1.833	
				60.00				45.00	2.444
								67.50	1.630
								90.00	1.222
								112.50	0.978
								135.00	0.815
								135.00	0.815
				20				30.00	90.00
			45.00		1.833				
			60.00		2.444				
			75.00		3.055				
			90.00		3.667				
			60.00		45.00	4.889			
					67.50	3.259			
					90.00	2.444			
					112.50	1.956			
					135.00	1.630			
					135.00	1.630			
			10		30.00	90.00	80.58	34.00	
				45.00	3.667				
				60.00	4.889				
				75.00	6.111				
				90.00	7.333				
				60.00	45.00				9.778
					67.50				6.518
					90.00				4.889
					112.50				3.911
					135.00				3.259
					135.00				3.259

Table S1. continued

	Seeding			Patch synthesis					
	Seed batch (Fig 5/6 only)	AuNc size acc. to Haiss et al. during seeding / nm	$\rho_{0,Seed}$ / -	$c(\text{AgNO}_3)$ / μM	$c(\text{s-SiO}_2)$ / mg/L	$c(\text{CH}_2\text{O})$ / mM	$c(\text{NH}_3)$ / mM	$n^* \times 10^{-6}$ / -	
Fig. 6 (for Seed A recipes see Fig. 5/S6)	B	3.8	40	20.00	145.00	80.58	34.00	0.253	
				32.50	120.00			0.497	
				45.00	110.00			0.750	
				50.00	92.00			0.996	
				56.00	82.00			1.252	
				60.00	73.50			1.497	
	C	3.5	60	60.00	90.00	80.58	34.00	0.810	
				60.00	112.50			0.652	
				60.00	135.00			0.543	
				60.00	157.50			0.466	
				60.00	180.00			0.407	
				45.00	180.00			0.306	
				30.00	180.00			0.204	
				20.00	225.00			0.109	
	D	4.1	60	60.00	180.00	80.58	34.00	0.407	
				20.00	225.00			0.109	
				60.25	160.00			0.460	
				45.50	150.00			0.371	
33.75				150.00	0.275				
25.00				170.00	0.180				
13.90				400.00	0.042				
Fig. 7		4.1	40	75.00	138.00	80.58	34.00	0.996	
Fig. S4		4.2	40	60.00	90.00	80.58	34.00	1.222	
			40 washed	60.00	90.00	80.58	34.00	1.222	
Fig. S7	C	3.5	60	11.00	540.00	80.58	34.00	0.025	
				45.00	180.00			0.306	
	A	4.3		40	60.00	90.00	80.58	34.00	1.222
				20	90.00	90.00			3.667
				10	60.00	90.00			4.889
				10	90.00	90.00			7.333

Figure S1. a) Number weighted size distribution of gold nanocrystals as determined by the automated analysis of 269 particles on TEM images (the same sample as shown in Figure 1a of the main article). \bar{x} refers to the average size in each histogram bin. b) UV-VIS-NIR extinction spectra of a gold nanocrystal seed batch regularly measured over several weeks, c) Evolution in of gold nanocrystal size as determined from b) using the analysis according to Haiss et al. [Anal. Chem. 2007, **79**, 4215]

Figure S2: Photographs of a seed stock with $\rho = 40$ shortly after seeding (left) and after standing for 120 minutes (right).

Figure S3. Low magnification SEM images of the samples shown in Figure 3 of the main article

Figure S4. Extinction spectra and SEM images of patchy particles synthesized at the same parameters with untreated and washed seeded core particles

Figure S5. Evidence for agglomerated seed nanocrystals and multiple seeds within a patch – a) HAADF-STEM image showing an agglomerate of gold nanocrystals on a silica core following seeding. b) HAADF-STEM image of a silver patch and, for the blue rectangular region, c) magnified image and EDX maps of d) Ag and e) Au net intensity signal.

Figure S6. Normalized extinction spectra of silver on silica patchy particle samples produced from seeded silica with seeding density a) $\rho_{0,\text{Seed}} = 20$ and b) $\rho_{0,\text{Seed}} = 10$ and variation of relative SiO_2 (top) or AgNO_3 (bottom) concentration in the patch growth process. Note that 100% relative concentration corresponds to the concentration used in the initial experiments (see Figure 3 and corresponding text).

Figure S7. SEM images of silver on silica patchy particles produced at a wide range of values of $n^* \times 10^{-6}$. The seed used corresponds to Seed C (top two images) and Seed A (bottom four images) as defined in Figure 6 of the main article. Note that in order to cover the wide range of n^* shown, different seeding densities needed to be used. Hence the number of patches per core particle differs.